

Informed consent form for participation in the experiment

“Elicitation of context-aware functionalities”

Researcher: Rodrigo Falcão (rodrigo.falcao@iese.fraunhofer.de), Fraunhofer IESE

About the research: Context-aware functionalities are functionalities that consider context to produce a certain system behavior, typically an adaptation or recommendation. For example, when YouTube automatically adapts the quality of the video you are watching based on the speed of your network connection, this is context awareness. Or when Instagram recommends a place to tag your new photo based on your location, this is also context awareness. As context information such as time, location, weather, user activity, device characteristics, network status, and countless others are becoming increasingly more accessible, the potential for adding context awareness to our applications is enormous. This research focuses on how to improve the elicitation of context-aware functionalities.

About the experiment:

- **Structure:** The experiment has 4 parts:
 - Part 1: Introduction to the elicitation of context-aware functionalities and to the experiment procedures (20-30 min)
 - Part 2: Briefing questionnaire (5 min)
 - Part 3: Elicitation of context-aware functionalities (30 min)
 - Part 4: Debriefing questionnaire (10-20 min)
- **Data collection:** Participants will actively provide data in parts 2, 3, and 4 via an online tool (“instrument”). In part 2, participants will be asked about their background and experience; in part 3, which is the main part of the experiment, participants will be asked to generate requirements that describe context-aware functionalities in a specific scenario that will be described to them; in part 4, participants will be asked some questions about the execution of the experiment itself.
- **Confidentiality:** To help protect your confidentiality, the instrument used to support the data collection in the experiment does **not** record any information that could personally identify you. All data will be stored in a password-protected location. Your responses will be kept confidential. The **anonymized** raw data collected will be publicly accessible for at least 10 years. Any insights gained will be used in the context of doctoral research. This may also include publication of the results (including aggregation of responses) in scientific publications.

Participation will give you an opportunity to be introduced to the elicitation of context-aware functionalities and receive information about what has been done in this research to improve it.

Comprehension and consent:

I understand the conditions for participating in the experiment and accept them. I had the opportunity to ask for clarification regarding the experiment as well as my role in it. I am aware that I have the right to withdraw from participating in this experiment without penalty at any time.

Name of Participant

Date and signature

Rodrigo Meneses Porto Falcão

Name of Researcher

Date and signature